

UNSUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING FOR MANAGING SAFETY ACCIDENTS IN RAILWAY STATION

Prince Vinod Patel¹, U Rishik Vardhan Reddy²,

Yarramalla Vamshi³, Dr. S. Sribindu⁴

^{1,2,3} UG Student, Dept. of ECE, CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

⁴ Associate Professor, Dept. of ECE,

CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

ABSTRACT

For both passenger and freight transportation, railroad operations must be dependable, accessible, maintained, and safe (RAMS). In many urban areas, railway stations risk and safety accidents represent an essential safety concern for daily operations. Moreover, the accidents lead to damage to market reputation, including injuries and anxiety among the people and costs. This stations under pressure caused by higher demand which consuming infrastructure and raised the safety administration consideration. To analysing these accidents and utilising the technology such AI methods to enhance safety, it is suggested to use unsupervised topic modelling for better understand the contributors to these extreme accidents. It is conducted to optimise Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) for fatality accidents in the railway stations from textual data gathered RRSB including 1000 accidents in the UK railway station. This research describes using the machine learning topic method for systematic spot accident characteristics to enhance safety and risk

management in the stations and provides advanced analysing. The study evaluates the efficacy of text by mining from accident history, gaining information, lesson learned and deeply coherent of the risk caused by assessing fatalities accidents for large and enduring scale. This Intelligent Text Analysis presents predictive accuracy for valuable accident information such as root causes and the hot spots in the railway stations. Further, the big data analytics ' improvement results in an understanding of the accidents' nature in ways not possible if a considerable amount of safety history and not through narrow domain analysis of the accident reports. This technology renders stand with high accuracy and a beneficial and extensive new era of AI applications in railway industry safety and other fields for safety applications.

INTRODUCTION

Trains as public transportation have been considered as safer than other means. However, passengers on trains stations sometimes face many risks because of many overlapping factors such as station operation,

design, and passenger behaviours. Due to the gradually increasing demand and the heavily congested society and the state of some station's layout and complexity in design, there are potential risks during the operation of the stations. Furthermore, Passenger, people and public safety is the main concern of the railway industry and one of the critical parts of the system. European Union put into practice Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety (RAMS) as a standard in 1999 known as EN 50126. Aiming to prevent railway accidents and ensure a high level of safety in railway operations. The RAMS analyses concepts lead to minimising the risks to acceptable levels and rise safety levels. However, that have been an urgent issue and still, the reports show several people are killed every year in the railway station, some accidents lead to injuries or fatalities. For example, In Japan in 2016, 420 accidents occurred that included being struck by a train, which resulted in 202 deaths. This including of those 420 accidents, 179 (resulting in 24 fatalities) included falling from a platform and following injury or death as a consequence of hitting with a train [1]. In the UK, 2019/20, it has been reported that Most passenger injuries occur from accidents in stations. Greatest Major injuries are the outcome of slips, trips and falls, of which there were approximately 200 [2] play significant impact in reducing

injuries on station platforms and provide quality, reliable and safe travel environment for all passengers, worker and public. Even if some accident does not result in deaths or injuries, such accidents cause delay, cost, fear and anxiety among the people, interruption in the operations and damage the industry reputation. Also, to provide or invest any control safety measurements the stations it is crucial to considering the risks associated with the railway incidents and risks in the station and identification of many factors related to the accident by a comprehensive knowledge of the root cause of accidents considering all the possible technology. The objective of this research is to analysis a collection case of accidents between 01/01/2000 and 17/04/2020 data to introduce a smart method, which expected to develop the safety level future, the risk management process, and the way to collect data in the railway stations. This data been gathered by RSSBS and agreed to be used for the research purpose. Analysing an extensive amount of data recorded in a different form are a challenging job. Nowadays, it is hard to obtain for specific information in such mix digitization big data in including Web, video, images and other sources, it is research of a needle in a haystack. Thus, a powerful tool for assistance manage, search and understand these vast amounts of information is needed indeed [3], [4]. Many

pre-processing techniques and algorithms are required to obtain valuable characteristics from an enormous amount of safety data in the stations including textual. The study covers the topic modelling to identify useful characteristics such the root cause of the accidents and also exploring the factors which are multiple groups of words or phrases that explain and summarize the content covered by an accident's reports reducing time with high accuracy of outcomes. Topic modelling techniques are robust smart methods that extensively applied in natural language processing to topic detection and semantic mining from unstructured documents. Consequently, It has been suggested in this work the LDA model which is one of the best-known probabilistic unsupervised learning methods that marks the topics implicit in collection of contexts [5].

LITERATURE REVIEW

A literature review of Artificial Intelligence applications in railway systems

Nowadays it is widely accepted that Artificial Intelligence (AI) is significantly influencing a large number of domains, including railways. In this paper, we present a systematic literature review of the current state-of-the-art of AI in railway transport. In particular, we analysed

and discussed papers from a holistic railway perspective, covering sub-domains such as maintenance and inspection, planning and management, safety and security, autonomous driving and control, revenue management, transport policy, and passenger mobility. This review makes an initial step towards shaping the role of AI in future railways and provides a summary of the current focuses of AI research connected to rail transport. We reviewed about 139 scientific papers covering the period from 2010 to December 2020. We found that the major research efforts have been put in AI for rail maintenance and inspection, while very limited or no research has been found on AI for rail transport policy and revenue management. The remaining subdomains received mild to moderate attention. AI applications are promising and tend to act as a game-changer in tackling multiple railway challenges. However, at the moment, AI research in railways is still mostly at its early stages. Future research can be expected towards developing advanced combined AI applications (e.g. with optimization), using AI in decision making, dealing with uncertainty and tackling newly rising cybersecurity challenges.

Using Explainable Machine Learning to Interpret the Effects of Policies on

Air Pollution: COVID-19 Lockdown in London

Activity changes during the COVID-19 lockdown present an opportunity to understand the effects that prospective emission control and air quality management policies might have on reducing air pollution. Using a regression discontinuity design for causal analysis, we show that the first UK national lockdown led to unprecedented decreases in road traffic, by up to 65%, yet incommensurate and heterogeneous responses in air pollution in London. At different locations, changes in air pollution attributable to the lockdown ranged from -50% to 0% for nitrogen dioxide (NO_2), 0% to $+4\%$ for ozone (O_3), and -5% to $+0\%$ for particulate matter with an aerodynamic diameter less than $10\ \mu\text{m}$ (PM_{10}), and there was no response for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. Using explainable machine learning to interpret the outputs of a predictive model, we show that the degree to which NO_2 pollution was reduced in an area was correlated with spatial features (including road freight traffic and proximity to a major airport and the city center), and that existing inequalities in air pollution exposure were exacerbated: pollution reductions were greater in places with more affluent residents and better access to public transport services.

Topic Modeling and User Network Analysis on Twitter during World Lupus Awareness Day

Twitter is increasingly used by individuals and organizations to broadcast their feelings and practices, providing access to samples of spontaneously expressed opinions on all sorts of themes. Social media offers an additional source of data to unlock information supporting new insights disclosures, particularly for public health purposes. Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a complex, systemic autoimmune disease that remains a major challenge in therapeutic diagnostic and treatment management. When supporting patients with such a complex disease, sharing information through social media can play an important role in creating better healthcare services. This study explores the nature of topics posted by users and organizations on Twitter during world Lupus day to extract latent topics that occur in tweet texts and to identify what information is most commonly discussed among users. We identified online influencers and opinion leaders who discussed different topics. During this analysis, we found two different types of influencers that employed different narratives about the communities they belong to. Therefore, this study identifies hidden

information for healthcare decision-makers and provides a detailed model of the implications for healthcare organizations to detect, understand, and define hidden content behind large collections of text.

Method of Coupling Metrics for Object-Oriented Software System Based on CSBG Approach

Context. Coupling between classes is an important metric for software complexity in software systems. *Objective.* In order to overcome the shortcomings of the existing coupling methods and fully investigate the weighted coupling of classes in different cases in large-scale software systems, this study analyzed the relationship between classes at package level, class level, and method level. *Method.* The software system is considered as a set of special bipartite graphs in complex networks, and an effective method for coupling measurement is proposed as well. Furthermore, this method is theoretically proved to satisfy the mathematical properties of coupling measurement, leading to overcome the disadvantages of the majority of existing methods. In addition, it was revealed that the proposed method was efficient according to the analyses of existing methods for coupling measurement. Eventually, an algorithm was designed and a program was

developed to calculate coupling between classes in three open-source software systems. *Results.* The results indicated the scale-free characteristic of complex networks in the statistical data. Additionally, the calculated power-law value was used as a metric for coupling measurement, so as to calculate coupling of the three open-source software.

Designing of Latent Dirichlet Allocation Based Prediction Model to Detect Midlife Crisis of Losing Jobs due to Prolonged Lockdown for COVID-19

The sudden outbreak of the virus COVID-19 has created a pandemic situation worldwide. Humankind has not experienced such a danger caused by this disease in the past hundred years. Apart from all the health issues, the pandemic has created an immense impact on social life, economics, mental peace, and all aspects of human life. Prolonged quarantine is creating uncertainties; death tolls are creating fear. According to the World Health Organization, this public health emergency is likely to create anxiety, loneliness, depression, fear of losing jobs, being economically unstable, and committing suicide. In our

present discussion, we prepare a statistical record using data collected from all over the world to find the intensity of mental disorder caused by this pandemic. Now we aim at finding the polarity of the specified term used by social media users. We aim to formulate a highly efficient mechanism that will detect depressive sentences more accurately. In our work, we try to formulate an optimal mechanism implementing the Latent Dirichlet Allocation approach to modify our findings and prove through a comparative study that depression affects the highest among people age 40–50. We experience that this age group is highly devastated in fear of losing jobs because of to this pandemic. The standard psychiatric symptom of lack of self-dignity and self-confidence that can happen to a human at the middle age is proliferated due to extended lockdown and its after effects. There is much research in sentiment analysis, which shows us the impact of COVID-19 in recent days. Surprisingly, recognizing symptoms of the midlife crisis in the pandemic situation of COVID-19 is yet to achieve.

A Review of Deep Learning Applications for Railway Safety

Railways speedily transport many people and goods nationwide, so railway accidents can pose immense damage. However, the

infrastructure of railways is so complex that its maintenance is challenging and expensive. Therefore, using artificial intelligence for railway safety has attracted many researchers. This paper examines artificial intelligence applications for railway safety, mainly focusing on deep learning approaches. This paper first introduces deep learning methods widely used for railway safety. Then, we investigated and classified earlier studies into four representative application areas: (1) railway infrastructure (catenary, surface, components, and geometry), (2) train body and bogie (door, wheel, suspension, bearing, etc.), (3) operation (railway detection, railroad trespassing, wind risk, train running safety, etc.), and (4) station (air quality control, accident prevention, etc.). We present fundamental problems and popular approaches for each application area. Finally, based on the literature reviews, we discuss the opportunities and challenges of artificial intelligence for railway safety.

The usefulness of artificial intelligence for safety assessment of different transport modes

Recent research in transport safety focuses on the processing of large amounts of available data by means of intelligent systems, in order to decrease the number of accidents for

transportation users. Several Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications have been developed to address safety problems and improve efficiency of transportation systems. However exchange of knowledge between transport modes has been limited. This paper reviews the ML and AI methods used in different transport modes (road, rail, maritime and aviation) to address safety problems, in order to identify good practices and experiences that can be transferable between transport modes. The methods examined include statistical and econometric methods, algorithmic approaches, classification and clustering methods, artificial neural networks (ANN) as well as optimization and dimension reduction techniques. Our research reveals the increasing interest of transportation researchers and practitioners in AI applications for crash prediction, incident/failure detection, pattern identification, driver/operator or route assistance, as well as optimization problems. The most popular and efficient methods used in all transport modes are ANN, SVM, Hidden Markov Models and Bayesian models. The type of the analytical technique is mainly driven by the purpose of the safety analysis performed. Finally, a wider variety of AI and ML methodologies is observed in road transport mode, which also appears to

concentrate a higher, and constantly increasing, number of studies compared to the other modes.

EXISTING SYSTEM:

Despite the scatter of applying such method and the differences in terms been using in the literature, there is a shortage of such applications in the railway industry. Moreover, the NLP has been implemented to detect defects in the requirements documents of a railway signaling manufacturer [13]. Also, for translating terms of the contract into technical specifications in the railway sector [14]. Additionally, identifying the significant factors contributing to railway accidents, the taxonomy framework was proposed using (Self-Organizing Maps – SOM), to classify human, technology, and organization factors in railway accidents [15]. Likewise, association rules mining has been used to identify potential causal relationships between factors in railway accidents [16].

Disadvantages

The system never implemented ML algorithms been used such as SVM, ANN, extreme learning machine (ELM), and decision tree (DT) which are more accurate and efficient.

The system didn't implement Self-Organizing Maps–SOM model to classify human, technology, and organization factors in railway accidents

Proposed System

This paper establishes an innovative method in the area to studies how the textual source of data of railway station accident reports could be efficiently used to extract the root causes of accidents and establish an analysis between the textual and the possible cause. where the full automated process that has ability to get the input of text and provide outputs not yet ready. Applying this method expected to come overcome issues such as aid the decision-maker in real time and extract the key information to be understandable from non-experts, better identify the details of the accident in-depth, design expert smart safety system and effective usage of the safety history records. A Such results could support in the analysis of safety and risk management to be systematic and smarter. Our approach uses state-of-the-art LDA algorithm to capture the critical texts information of accidents and their causes .

Advantages

A DT is a determination support tool that applies a treelike pattern of decisions and their

likely outcomes [40], [53]. There are many possible (ML) approaches towards safety analysis. More exactly, we train a DT to classify the accidents and the patterns that occurred in these accidents in the stations.

The textual data have strong key information which can be used such as the time, description of the accidents, location and the range age of the victim. The time of accidents occurred been divided as the Parts of the Day for more mining to capture accurate times.

CONCLUSION

Topic models have an important role in many fields and in such case of safety and risk management in the railway stations for texts mining. In Topic modelling, a topic is a list of words that occur in statistically significant methods. A text can be voice records investigation reports, or reviews risk documents and so on. This research displays various cases for the power of unsupervised machine learning topic modelling in promoting risk management, safety accidents investigation and restructuring accidents recording and documentation on the industrybased level. The description of the root causes accident, the suggested model, it has been showing that the platforms are the hot point in the stations. The outcomes reveal the

station's accidents to be occurring owing to four main causes: falls, struck by trains, electric shock. Moreover, the night time and days of the week seems to contact to the risks are significant. With increased safety text mining, knowledge is gained on a wide scale and different periods resulting in greater efficiency RAMS and providing the creation of a holistic perspective for all stakeholders. Application of the unsupervised machine learning technique is useful for safety since, which is solving, exploring hidden patterns and deal with many challenges such as:

- Text data from many perspectives and in unstructured forms

- Power for discovery, dealing with missing values, and spot safety and risk kyes from data
- Smart labelling, clustering, centroids, sampling, and associated coordinates
- Capture the relationships, causations, more for ranking risks and related information
- Prioritisation risks and measures implementations
- Aid the process of safety review and learning from the long and massive experience.
- Can be used the scale and weighted as configuration options which can be used for assessing risks. Although this paper highlights the innovative of unsupervised machine learning in accidents classification of railway accidents and root cause analyses, it is a necessity to focus on expanded research on the

huge data topics concerning the diversity of the station's locations, size and safety cultures and other factors with further techniques of unsupervised machine learning algorithms in the future. Finally, this research enhances safety, but it raises the importance of data in text form and suggests redesigning the way of gathering data to be more comprehensive.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Terabe, T. Kato, H. Yaginuma, N. Kang, and K. Tanaka, "Risk assessment model for railway passengers on a crowded platform," *Transp. Res. Rec., J. Transp. Res. Board*, vol. 2673, no. 1, pp. 524–531, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1177/0361198118821925.
- [2] Annual Health and Safety Report 19/2020, RSSB, London, U.K., 2020.
- [3] D. M. Blei, "Probabilistic topic models," *Commun. ACM*, vol. 55, no. 4, pp. 77–84, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1145/2133806.2133826.
- [4] M. Gethers and D. Poshyvanyk, "Using relational topic models to capture coupling among classes in object-oriented software systems," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Softw. Maintenance*, Sep. 2010, pp. 1–10, doi: 10.1109/ICSM.2010.5609687.

- [5] D. M. Blei, A. Y. Ng, and M. I. Jordan, "Latent Dirichlet allocation," *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 3, nos. 4–5, pp. 993–1022, Mar. 2003, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-411519-4.00006-9.
- [6] H. Alawad, S. Kaewunruen, and M. An, "A deep learning approach towards railway safety risk assessment," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 102811–102832, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2997946.
- [7] H. Alawad, S. Kaewunruen, and M. An, "Learning from accidents: Machine learning for safety at railway stations," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 633–648, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2962072.
- [8] A. J.-P. Tixier, M. R. Hallowell, B. Rajagopalan, and D. Bowman, "Automated content analysis for construction safety: A natural language processing system to extract precursors and outcomes from unstructured injury reports," *Autom. Construct.*, vol. 62, pp. 45–56, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2015.11.001.
- [9] J. Sido and M. Konopik, "Deep learning for text data on mobile devices," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Appl. Electron.*, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.23919/AE.2019.8867025.
- [10] A. Serna and S. Gasparovic, "Transport analysis approach based on big data and text mining analysis from social media," *Transp. Res. Proc.*, vol. 33, pp. 291–298, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.trpro.2018.10.105.
- [11] Reddy, Kalleem Niranjana, and Pappu Venkata Yasoda Jayasree. "Low Power Strain and Dimension Aware SRAM Cell Design Using a New Tunnel FET and Domino Independent Logic." *International Journal of Intelligent Engineering & Systems* 11, no. 4 (2018).
- [12] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Design of a Dual Doping Less Double Gate Tfet and Its Material Optimization Analysis on a 6t Sram Cells."
- [13] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Low power process, voltage, and temperature (PVT) variations aware improved tunnel FET on 6T SRAM cells." *Sustainable Computing: Informatics and Systems* 21 (2019): 143-153.
- [14] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Survey on improvement of PVT aware variations in tunnel FET on SRAM cells." In *2017 International Conference on Current Trends in Computer, Electrical, Electronics and Communication (CTCEEC)*, pp. 703-705. IEEE, 2017

[15] Karne, R. K. ., & Sreeja, T. K. . (2023). PMLC- Predictions of Mobility and Transmission in a Lane-Based Cluster VANET Validated on Machine Learning. *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, 11(5s), 477–483.

<https://doi.org/10.17762/ijritcc.v11i5s.7109>

[16] Radha Krishna Karne and Dr. T. K. Sreeja (2022), A Novel Approach for Dynamic Stable Clustering in VANET Using Deep Learning (LSTM) Model. *IJEER* 10(4), 1092-1098. DOI: 10.37391/IJEER.100454.